

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

DIFFERENT WAYS TO STIMULATE GERMINATION OF COTTON SEEDS STORED FOR A LONG TIME IN GENBANK CONDITIONS

Mammadova S.,

*PhD in biology, Associate Professor
Institute of Genetic Resources of MNO, Baku*

Mammadova N.,

*PhD in biology, Associate Professor
Institute of Genetic Resources of MNO, Baku*

Jafarova E.,

*PhD in biology,
Institute of Genetic Resources of MNO, Baku*

Bakhshieva N.,

*PhD in biology,
Institute of Genetic Resources of MNO, Baku*

Akhmedova V.

*Researcher
Institute of Genetic Resources of MNO, Baku
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12580370>*

Abstract

The article reflects the results of studying the effect of electromagnetic radiation of millimeter range on seeds of different samples of cotton, stored for a long time in the National Genebank of Azerbaijan and determining the optimal dose and method of exposure for the most effective stimulation of germination. The treatment was carried out on both dry and soaked seeds, as well as distilled water intended for irrigation of experimental seeds. Evaluation of germination energy and seed viability was carried out by laboratory germination test. Analysis of the obtained data revealed the germination stimulating effect of certain doses and exposures. The greatest increase in germination was observed at the dose of 180 Vt/dm³/120 seconds in all samples involved in the study. The pattern of suppressive effect of 900 Vt/dm³/120 seconds dose at direct exposure of seeds was also revealed, although the indirect effect of 900 Vt/dm³ dose through water stimulated seed germination.

Keywords: cotton, seeds, storage, germination, electromagnetic radiation

The cotton collection of the National Genebank of Azerbaijan has more than a thousand samples. Maintaining the viability of germplasm of plant genetic resources in an active state is one of the main tasks of Genebanks. Since the aging process of seeds is inevitable even under optimal conditions of long-term storage, the search for new ways and methods to increase the safety of seed material is relevant. The analysis of literature data has shown that the effect of electromagnetic radiation of millimeter range on living objects has a non-thermal, regulatory character and favorably affects their viability [1; 2; 3]. The work of S.M. Orekhova points to the acceleration of seed germination processes and the beneficial effect on seeds of pretreatment for 9 minutes of a magnetic field with an induction of 8 mTl and a frequency of 16 Hz [4]. I.I. Shamgunov notes that when wheat seeds are treated in the microwave oven mode of operation at low and medium power consumption, a significant increase in the biomass of seed germination is observed within 60 seconds [5]. In the work of Z.H.-M. Khashayev it is shown that distilled water irradiated with electromagnetic radiation is able to transfer the effect of exposure to biological systems, i.e., seeds involved in germination [6]. Therefore, we have attempted to use electromagnetic radiation to test the possibility of stimulating the germination of seeds whose viability has decreased due to prolonged storage

in cold storage [7]. In addition, the use of radiation of the millimeter range is more promising and effective than the use of other physical factors. Unlike chemical methods, electromagnetic radiation of the millimeter range when applied affects the vitality of plants and at the same time does not have any ecologically harmful effect on the environment.

The aim of the research was to study the effect of electromagnetic radiation of millimeter range on seeds of different cotton samples stored for a long time in the National Genebank of Azerbaijan and to determine the optimal dose and method of exposure to stimulate germination.

Materials and methods

During the search for ways to preserve the quality of seeds stored in the refrigerated chamber of National Genebank, experiments were conducted to study the effect of electromagnetic radiation of millimeter range on the example of seeds of a number of cotton samples - Agdash-6, Agdash-3, AP-331, AP-154, AP-157, Ganja-158, AG 2153.

Viability (G) was assessed in two repetitions by laboratory seed germination test expressed as a percentage of the total number of seeds planted (n):

$$G = \frac{A \times 100\%}{n}$$
, where A is the number of germinated seeds

The relative change in germination (V) was calculated using the formula:

$V = \frac{M - M_0}{M_0}$, where M - % of experimental germinated seeds, M_0 - % of control germinated seeds.

At the initial stage of the study, the duration and strength of exposure to microwave radiation for seeds of each plant were selected in such a combination that the stimulation of seed germination was achieved. The equipment used was a Samsung C105AR/C105ABR microwave oven (230Vt/50Hz, 100Vt/900Vt power output unit, EC-705 standard, operating frequency 2450MHz, chamber volume - 28L). In the first experiment, 3 power units (180 Vt/dm³, 450 Vt/dm³, 900Vt/dm³) and 2 exposures (20 and 120 sec.) were used for seed treatment. In the second, doses - 450 Vt/dm³ and 600Vt/dm³ and 2 exposures (40 and 80 sec.) were used to treat the seeds. In the third experiment, electromagnetic ray treatment at a dose of 900 Vt/dm³ was used for 5, 10 and 15 seconds distilled water was used. In the fourth, treatment of soaked seeds

with doses of 300Vt/dm³ and 450 Vt/dm³ for 40 seconds and irrigation of seeds with distilled water treated with the same doses were used. Each series of experiments was accompanied by creation of equal conditions for germination of seeds of all tested plants.

Results and discussion

Seed germination and germination energy are the main indicators of seed quality. To determine the optimal dose and exposure of electromagnetic radiation stimulating germination of seeds of technical crops, 3 power units (180 Vt/dm³, 450 Vt/dm³, 900Vt/dm³) and 2 exposures (20 and 120 sec.) were used for 4 samples of cotton (*Gossypium* L. - Agdash-6, AP-331, AP-154, AP-157) stored in Genebank. As can be seen from Picture 1, for seeds of all cotton samples the applied combinations of dose and exposure time except for the highest one (900 Vt/dm³/120 sec.), at which seed germination decreased by 4.0-8.0%, turned out to be stimulating. The most effective dose was 180 Vt/dm³/120 sec.

Pic. 1. Effect of electromagnetic radiation on seed germination of 4 cotton samples

In the second experiment on the example of Agdash-3 variety, the combination of 2 units of radiation power (450 V/dm³ and 600 V/dm³) and 2 exposures (40 and 80 sec) was chosen. As can be seen from Picture 2 cotton seeds stored for a long time in the cold chamber had low (70.0%) germination in the control. Differences in germination of cotton seeds were observed after irradiation with different doses. When seeds were

treated with a dose of 600 W/dm³ for 80 seconds, stimulation of seed germination was observed. Decreasing the duration of this dose resulted in even greater stimulation of seed germination. As a result of exposure to rays of such power, seed germination increased by 25.0% and amounted to 95.0%. Thus, the most optimal dose was 600 W/dm³ with duration of action - 40 seconds.

Pic.2 Effect of short-wave radiation on germination of cotton seeds (Agdash -3)

In further studies on the example of Ganja - 158 variety, the seeds of which were stored in the cold room for 11 years, it was revealed that treatment of soaked

seeds with 900Vt/dm³ dose for 5, 10 and 15 seconds increased the number of germinated seeds by 6.0, 14.0 and 20.0% (Picture 3).

Pic.3 Germination of cotton seeds (Ganja - 158) treated with irradiated water

Further, it was of interest to identify the differences in the response of cotton seeds to the treatment of soaked seeds with doses of 300Vt/dm³ and 450 Vt/dm³ for 40 seconds and irrigation of seeds with distilled wa-

ter treated with the same doses. An increase in germination of 6.0 - 8.0% was observed in the former case and 10.0 - 14.0% in the latter. Thus, it can be concluded that treatment with irradiated water had a more effective effect.

Pic. 4. Effect of microwave radiation on germination energy and germination of soaked cotton seeds (AG-2153)

Analyzing the data on the effect of electromagnetic irradiation on germination of seeds of different cotton samples presented in summary Table 1 revealed stimulating germination combinations of doses and exposures. The greatest increase in germination was observed at the dose of 180 Vt/dm³/120 seconds in all

samples involved in the study. The pattern of suppressive effect of 900 Vt/dm³/120 sec. dose at direct exposure of seeds was also revealed, although the indirect effect of 900 Vt/dm³ dose through water stimulated seed germination.

Table 1

Results of analysis of the obtained data on the effect of electromagnetic irradiation on seed germination of different cotton samples

Sample	Dose/exposure	EMI treatment			Relative change in germination, $\frac{M-M_0}{M_0}$
		seeds	water	soaked seeds	
		Increase in germination, %			
Agdash-6	180 Vt/dm ³ /20 s.	10,0			0,16
	180 Vt/dm ³ /120 s.	30,0			0,48
	450 Vt/dm ³ /20 s.	14,0			0,22
	450 Vt/dm ³ /120 s.	18,0			0,29
	900 Vt/dm ³ /20 s.	22,0			0,35
	900 Vt/dm ³ /120 s.	-6,0			-0,09
AP-331	180 Vt/dm ³ /20 s.	16,0			0,28
	180 Vt/dm ³ /120 s.	24,0			0,42
	450 Vt/dm ³ /20 s.	20,0			0,35
	450 Vt/dm ³ /120 s.	20,0			0,35
	900 Vt/dm ³ /20 s.	24,0			0,42
	900 Vt/dm ³ /120 s.	-4,0			-0,07
AP-154	180 Vt/dm ³ /20 s.	16,0			0,26
	180 Vt/dm ³ /120 s.	36,0			0,6
	450 Vt/dm ³ /20 s.	16,0			0,26
	450 Vt/dm ³ /120 s.	24,0			0,4
	900 Vt/dm ³ /20 s.	20,0			0,33
	900 Vt/dm ³ /120 s.	-4,0			-0,06
AP-157	180 Vt/dm ³ /20 s.	8,0			0,15
	180 Vt/dm ³ /120 s..	24,0			0,46
	450 Vt/dm ³ /20 s..	16,0			0,3
	450 Vt/dm ³ /120 s.	20,0			0,38
	900 Vt/dm ³ /20 s.	20,0			0,38
	900 Vt/dm ³ /120 s.	-8,0			-0,15
Agdash-3	450 Vt/dm ³ /40 s.	0			-
	450 Vt/dm ³ /80 s.	15,0			0,21
	600 Vt/dm ³ /40 s.	25,0			0,35
	600 Vt/dm ³ /80 s.	10,0			0,14
Ganja-158	900 Vt/dm ³ /5 s.		6,0		0,07
	900 Vt/dm ³ /10 s.		14,0		0,17
	900 Vt/dm ³ /15 s.		20,0		0,25
AzGR 10240	300 Vt/dm ³ /40 s.		10,0		0,17
	450 Vt/dm ³ /40 s.		14,0		0,25
	300 Vt/dm ³ /40 s.			6,0	0,1
	450 Vt/dm ³ /40 s.			8,0	0,14

Conclusion

Thus, the analysis of the obtained data on the effect of electromagnetic radiation on germination of cotton seeds stored for a long time in a refrigerated chamber revealed the effect of stimulating seed germination by certain doses and exposures. Early germination of seeds was characteristic for all experimental variants in comparison with control variants. The most effective was the treatment of seeds of different cotton samples with the dose of 180 Vt/dm³ for 120 seconds.

References:

1. Corlateanu L.B. Viability of cultivated plants seeds in conditions of *ex situ* conservation under the action of millimeter radiation (monograph). S.N.Maslobrod, A.I.Gania. Academy of Sciences of Moldova, Institute of Genetics and Plant Physiology. K: B, 2012, 156 p.
2. Logachev A.V., Zapletina A.V., Bastron A.V. Investigation of the influence of modes of pre-sowing

treatment of seeds of green crops with microwave energy on laboratory germination // Vestnik Kras GAU. 2017. №1. pp.77-84

3. Rozmetov, K. S. Technology of microwave pre-sowing treatment of cotton seeds in the conditions of Turkmenistan // Young Scientist. 2013, № 6 (53), pp. 123-127 URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/53/7194/>

4. Orekhova S.M. Influence of magnetic field of different configurations on germination of lentil seeds // Grain legumes and cereal crops. 2023. 2(46), pp. 66-73. DOI:10.24412/2309-348X-2023-2-66-73

5. Shamgunov I.I., Stepura A.V. Research of influence of pre-sowing microwave exposure on morphological indices of germinating spring wheat seeds// Engineering Vestnik Don, No.2, (2017). Electronic scientific journal "Engineering Vestnik Don", 2007-2017 ivdon.ru/en/magazine/archive/n2y2017/4243

6. Khashaev Z.Kh.-M., Cojocar A.F., Shekshiev E.M. Influence of EMI-irradiated distilled

water on plant objects // Izvestia TRTU. Thematic issue. "Intellectual CAD". 1999. pp.274-281

7. Mammadova S.A., Akhmadova V.E., Guliyeva S., Akhundova E.M. Stimulation of seed germination by electromagnetic

radiation//International Scientific Journal "Actual Research", Belgorod: LLC Agency for Advanced Scientific Research (APNI). 2023, №2(132). pp. 22-25
URL: <https://apni.ru/article/5339-stimulyatsiya-prorastaniya-semyan-elektromagn>